

PC Cost and Businesses Size

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Abstract – This researches will survey whether big business or the small business have more expensive use of PC's. Many businesses want to know about the cost of PC's for the use across the business. This researches will look to find the connections between the size of the businesses (small or large) and the cost of the PC's. The researches find that the PC's cost increase with businesses revenue and size.

Keywords—Cost, Computer, Small Business (key words)

I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

Many business use PC's for business tasks including processing invoices and orders not to mention electronic bookkeeping and such as this. Today businesses find the PC's are essential to commercial transactions with the customers. After the Electronic Commerce Act (Republic Act 8792) the business wish to know the cost of how their technology are doing for business opportunities.

But recently there are some debates about whether the size of the business will affect the cost of implementation in PC's across the business. The PC use is in many areas of the business for usefulness and employee satisfaction.

The main problem in this researches is that the business with the PC's may be paying greater costs. Using the PC's may have different costs if they are the big business or the small business. This researches aim to determine if PC's are more expensive to use in big business with the greater staff numbers. Staff and employees using the PC have greater need for accessing the processing power today and so we need to determine whether the cost of these is higher.

For this researches we conducted the survey of businesses in greater Western Mindanao region.

II. THE RESEARCH ON PC'S USE

It is common today for business of all kinds of industry to be using the PC for a wide range of business process. The business services is expected to be modern for the e-business to flourish. The researches from Jutla et al. (2001) show that keeping the customers depend on having a good PC strategy which also help the e-business. Also, the

researches from Korner and Zimmerman (2000) show that the information and communication technology (ICT) is growing for business to take advantage of e-business.

Having the PC'S for each employee in the business increases the costs of completing the work by making the technology more expensive for the business and also more management is required to keep the technology going. Keeping the cost low is important to the business.

III. BUSINESSES SIZE

The business change the cost to operate the business function. A small business is not alike to a big business. The researches of Rensleigh and Olivier (1998) tell us that affordability and cost have a different effect in the small business.

The big business does not only mean more business employees even though big business may mean more bureaucratic (Stott and Wood 2001).

More employees may have more PC's, along with a bigger size in big business. There are two ways to measure the size of the business. One is the number of business employees and the other is the revenues in the business (Goode 2001). To be sure of having the business size the researches use both of them. It also need the special expertise to keep the PC's going which means the additional cost is higher for them (Gill and Pidduck 2001). Business with more business employees have higher business cost and business with more employees have higher PC's cost. The hypothesis means:

Business with greater business size have higher PC's cost.

Business may make more profit with the PC's than without the PC's. The hypothesis means:

Business with higher business revenue have higher PC's cost.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This researches has asked 300 business to participate in our survey about PC's cost in the business. We survey the

businesses of greater Western Mindanao region including Zamboanga City and Davao City.

110 business kindly replied about the PC use and cost, and also the servers for file hosting and databases, with the survey response rate of 36%.

Of the industry, 22 sample members were in fishing and seafood manufacturing, 45 sample members were in retail, 10 were in diverse services. Two sample members did not divulge their industry.

Table 1 give the demographic informations of the survey members. All of the sample members used PC's but there was a difference in the number of the PC's for each business employee.

TABLE I. DEMOGRAPHIC OF THE SURVEY BUSINESS

<i>Business Type</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Retailers	45	40.9
Fishing and seafood manufacturing	22	20
IT	16	14.5
Food and beverages	15	13.6
Diverse services	10	9
Not stated	2	1.8
Total	110	100
<i>Business Size</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percent</i>
1-10 employees	23	20.9
10-20 employees	41	37.2
20-30 employees	26	23.6
30-40 employees	16	14.5
40-100 employees	4	3.6
Total	110	100

The researches analyse the sample members data and compare the sample members with employees and revenues. First we have analyse the employees size in the first figure 1. The chart show that most business spend less than around ₱200,000 but some spend much more than that. But also there are other business that have greater employees while spending little on the PC's.

Figure 1. Business size and PC's cost

Second we have analyse the revenues size in the second figure2. The chart show that most business have less than around ₱1,000,000 revenue according to the sample. But some business have lower PC's cost even with the same revenues.

Figure 1 Business revenues and PC's Cost

The researches analyses show that the business size relate to the cost of the PC's. If the business is big, the cost of the PC's is higher. If the business is small, the cost of the PC's is lower. But the measurements of the business size change the impact of the PC's cost in the result. In the number of employees the result is different to the revenues size. The size may affect the first-mover advantage in competition (Brown 2001).

V. CONCLUSION

In this researches we have found out about the way for PC's in the small business. We are continue to do the researches.

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